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Identifying the critical software underpinning UKRI DRI

UKRI DRI Congress 2025, Leeds

UK Research
and Innovation

Overview

REPORT:

bit.ly/critical-software

- Context of this work - findings from our research
- Interactive poll: your perceptions of risks to software
- Group discussions
 - Identifying software at risk
 - Recommending potential mitigations
 - Feeding back
- Interactive poll: what software do you think is at risk and why?

Report: Thomas, B., Chue Hong, N., & Hettrick, S. (2025). Understanding Critical Software for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16848311>

Overview of Critical Software Study

Background

- **Desire to understand some of the issues around supporting DRI investment**
- Research:
 - Interviews with 6 UKRI digital research infrastructures
 - ARCHER2
 - Isambard AI
 - JASMIN
 - DARE-UK (Programme team)
 - iDAH (Seshat Global History Databank)
 - PSDI
 - Focus groups with staff and users of Compute and Data infrastructures
- Analysis and Writing up
 - Definitions of 'Critical Software'
 - Risk
 - Audits

Definitions of ‘Critical Software’

- There being **no viable alternative**
 - Discussed in relation to the cost or effort required to switch. Concerns here were tied to the resources that infrastructures had to address software challenges.
- The **negative consequences** of software no longer working.
 - This was discussed as affecting either the whole or part of the software stack, the severity of the failure, being an imminent consequence or at sometime in the future, and in relation to how much each person is affected vs. how many people are affected.

Risks to critical software

- Limited or no **maintenance** from developers or communities
- A **lack of internal skilled staff** to support/maintain software
- **Licensing** changes
- Cost of **support** from commercial providers
- Changes in **governance**
- **Security** failures
- Incorrect/immature **code**

- Cross-cutting themes
 - Funding & lack of risk assessment/audit

Audits

- Audits were of value to those infrastructures that had conducted them, with many participants understanding their value in revealing the risks to critical software
- Many wanted support in conducting audits
- Infrastructures of different sizes and at different points in the life cycle require different kinds of audit

Recommendations

- Conducting an audit provides information on which to act on to better prevent or fix software failure
 - Identify risks
 - Understand scale of potential failures
 - Earlier decisions on maintain/repair
 - Time to find alternatives
 - Time to consider finding other mitigation strategies
- Audits might look different for different infrastructures
 - Age, size, funding, pace of change
- **More work needed on finding the best options**

Other Recommendations

- Support **information sharing** of risks (e.g., security, governance) between infrastructures.
 - This could be as part of a comprehensive community organisation along the lines of the Society of RSE, or a simple Slack workspace or email list.
- **Succession planning.**
 - Supporting getting the next generation people from the UK research community on software decision-making boards.
- **Invest in training and resources** for proper testing and V&V.
 - Supports software quality. Especially important for code developed from research grants that lack the resources of other software providers.

Perceptions of risk

Which software did you use most recently in your professional role?

Which software did you most recently use in your professional role?

Copilot

Excel

Excel

Office365

Outlook

Outlook

Slido

Teams

Atlas.ti

Chrome

Jira

Monday.com

Slack

SWIFT

Vim

**Which of these risks to software do you see most often in your job?
(Choose your top three)**

Which of these risks to software do you think will have become more important to assess in 3-5 years time? (Choose your top three)

Which of these risks to software do you see most often in your job? (Choose your top three)

Multiple Choice Poll 18 votes 18 participants

Which of these risks to software do you think will have become more important to assess in 3-5 years time? (Choose your top three)

Multiple Choice Poll 16 votes 16 participants

Are there any other risks to software that we've missed?

Are there any other risks to software that we've missed?

- Strategic shifts
 - Government drive towards certain areas of scientific software causing skilled staff to train towards “where the money is” meaning there isn’t the skilled staff in the software areas outside of these
 - More emphasis on building web tools to make research available and security implications of this
 - Lack of recognition in the value of research codes based on current bias in research funding
- Impact of Artificial Intelligence
 - Loss of IP due to uncontrolled use of AI in code development
 - Becoming more AI generated
- Interaction between research and software
 - Not understanding the basic science underlying the code
 - Limiting research because the software paradigms haven’t kept up
- Dealing with legacy code
 - Legacy code in unexpected places
 - Interdependencies
 - Too much of it? Compounding legacy
 - Abandoned dependencies
 - Continued use of a product/package when the researcher should using something else
- Increasingly complex software, harder for users to understand / people to maintain.
- Lack of obvious shared approaches

Group discussions

Group discussions

- You are going to work in groups based around the types of risks identified in the report
- The next 35 minutes split between these questions:
 - Discuss and identify the types of software that might be most exposed to that risk
 - Discuss and recommend potential mitigations and solutions for that risk
- Consider all the different types of mitigations, from knowledge sharing to strategic interventions
 - Don't just put "funding": say what you'd use the funding for
- Notes folder: https://bit.ly/DRI25_criticalsoftware

Feeding back

- One member of each group to feedback to the workshop
- Be succinct so there is time for discussion
 - One example of a type of software / piece of software exemplifying that risk
 - Top three recommendations for mitigations
 - If you can, choose one recommendation which is a “quick win” and one which is a longer, complex solution to implement

Discussion

1. Identify the types of software that might be most exposed to the risk assigned to your group (15 minutes)
2. Discuss and recommend potential mitigations and solutions for that risk (20 minutes)

Decide on one software and three mitigations to report back

https://bit.ly/DRI25_criticalsoftware

Feeding back

- One member of each group to feedback to the workshop
- Be succinct so there is time for questions
- One example of a type of software / piece of software exemplifying that risk
- Top three recommendations for mitigations

Reporting back

Group 1 - Maintenance

Software dependencies

- 1) Prioritise good code hygiene (e.g. using tools like Dependabot)
- 2) Encourage use of Software Bill of Materials
- 3) Move to promoting programming languages that are better at handling dependencies (e.g. Rust)

Hygiene and SBOMs shared with Group 2

Group 2 - Security & Immature Code

Software used on Trusted Research Environments

- 1) Encourage users to use software versions supplied by TRE infrastructure providers, rather than bringing their own
- 2) Provide better training for users on the risks related to security
- 3) Restrictions placed on software for security reasons should be framed as enablers

Reporting back

Group 3 - Licensing and Governance

VMWare raising it's annual licensing prices by 10x

- 1) Pooling effort for customising / supporting open source alternatives
- 2) Support for helping DRI to price their software (what's the market value of the tools we produce?)
- 3) Audits for software to feed into risk registers
 - a) Regular survey across institutions on top three concerns?
 - b) Sharing "early warning / red flags" e.g. VC buy out of software vendor

Group 4 - Cost of Support

KML Visualizer

- 1) Communicate the cost of software maintenance
- 2) More software maintenance grants
- 3) Don't underestimate costs on grants

Could SSI encourage anonymous sharing and publishing of the things that people don't like to share, such as costs, number of users, etc, to make it easier for the community to make better decisions?

What software is critical?

What software do you consider critical for UK research, but is at risk? (Include the name of the software and the risks)

What software do you consider critical for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure, but is at risk? (Include the name of the software and the risks)

What software is at risk?

Not sure if at risk, but **research data repository systems** (being bought by commercial and lock-ins)

Tidyverse - the R data processing packages. Risks include fragmentation and bloat

Kubernetes - skills competition with banks etc

The Funding Service - needs to be fit for use

lustre - skills, expertise (lack of)

CEPH - skills, finance

Easy to use software for **managing Python and Python packages** (risk with changes in Anaconda licence).

Workflow management packages (e.g. Nextflow). Risks include fragmentation and security implications

Openstack

Online Git hosting. Big reliance on GitHub with few alternatives.

Mature **Software Development Environments** for multiple vendor environments i.e, AMD vs CUDA / NVIDIA

AAAI integration (will it ever be comprehensive?) Risk of never being developed or not comprehensive across the whole research landscape

All the **national asset research data** in locked out of access software

Package management (singularity/apptainer) risk is fragmentation

Wrap up

- Thank you for participating!
- We will be doing follow-on work to:
 - Develop and pilot a framework for helping with software audits
 - Identify key areas of software and risks where mitigations can be implemented e.g. improving knowledge exchange, governance, or training and guidance
- If you are interested in collaborating, please get in touch
 - info@software.ac.uk
- *Report: Understanding Critical Software for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16848311>*

Thank you

Data collection

- Interviews with 6 UKRI digital research infrastructures
 - ARCHER2
 - Isambard AI
 - JASMIN
 - DARE-UK
 - iDAH (Seshat Global History Databank)
 - PSDI
- Focus groups
 - Compute
 - Data
- Desk research on software

Data analysis & writing up

- Making sense of software stacks
- Thematic coding of qualitative data
- Pivot from developing a list of critical software to trying to understand a range of issues around critical software
- Writing up into main themes
 - Definitions of 'Critical Software'
 - Risk
 - Audits